

Life Cycle Assessment for the electric steelmaking route in the ALCHIMIA project

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This contribution presents the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework developed within the ALCHIMIA project to support the environmental optimization of electric steelmaking. The LCA model establishes a baseline for three industrial EAF-based steel plants and provides impact factors to be integrated in a multi-objective optimization system. Results highlight the key environmental hotspots such as ferroalloys and electricity use, supporting data-driven improvements toward more sustainable metallurgy.

KEYWORDS: LCA, OPTIMIZATION, SCRAPS, FERROALLOYS, STEELMAKING, ELECTRIC ARC FURNACE

INTRODUCTION

The “Data and decentralized Artificial intelligence for a competitive and green European metallurgy industry” (ALCHIMIA) project aims at enhancing the competitiveness and environmental performance of the European metallurgy industry through data-driven and AI-based solutions. Among the different tools developed within the project, the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework plays a central role in evaluating the environmental profile of electric steelmaking processes based on Electric Arc Furnaces (EAF). Three CELSA Group plants and one cast iron foundry (Fonderia di Torbole, FdT) were involved in the LCA study, although only the steelmaking facilities were included in the optimization framework.

The LCA activities serve two main purposes: first, establishing a baseline environmental profile for the assessed steelmaking processes; second, providing environmental impact factors to support multi-objective optimization tools aiming at reducing both environmental burdens and production costs (Rossi et al., 2025).

LCA FRAMEWORK

The LCA methodology was applied according to the ISO 14040 and 14044 standards (International Organization for Standardization, 2022a, 2022b), following a cradle-to-gate approach. The functional unit was defined as 1 kg of liquid steel at the exit of the ladle furnace (LF). The system boundaries included the EAF, the LF, and all related inputs and outputs (e.g., scrap types, additives, energy use, emissions, and waste).

Primary data were collected in close collaboration with the CELSA plants, which provided either heat-level or annual production information. One plant (referred to as “Celsa 1”), in particular, served as a reference for filling data gaps across the other plants. For each facility, life cycle inventories (LCIs) were created, accounting for material consumption, electricity use, water input, and waste generation, in addition to ecoinvent 3.9.1 cut-off version as background database (Frischknecht, 2010). The Environmental Footprint EF 3.1 (Damiani et

al., 2022) was used as life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) method, with focus on climate change, acidification, eutrophication, ozone depletion, and photochemical ozone formation (Santero and Hendry, 2016).

A web-based LCA tool was developed to calculate the environmental impacts of individual production heats, making it possible to dynamically integrate LCA results into optimization routines. This digital module allows real-time feedback for adjusting scrap mix and process parameters.

The baseline environmental profile highlights two main hotspots: the consumption of ferroalloys (particularly silicomanganese and ferrosilicon) and electricity use, which varies significantly depending on the national energy mix of the plant location. For some impact categories, other relevant contributions include direct emissions, and waste management.

The analysis confirms that the output steel grade plays a significant role in determining environmental impacts due to varying amounts of tapping additions. These findings provide critical insights for the development of optimization algorithms, particularly in selecting the most influential parameters for impact reduction.

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